

Determination of the Mechanical Properties of Adhesives for Use in Design of Bonded Joints in Composite Structures

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ABSTRACT

Tensile properties obtained from bulk adhesive uniaxial tensile tests were used to predict the behaviour of a thick adherend lap shear joint using finite element analysis. The predicted behaviour of the joint was then compared with the behaviour observed experimentally. Both the von Mises and Drucker's yield criteria predicted the shear yield stress very well. However, a substantial discrepancy was found between the predicted shear modulus and the experimentally determined value. This discrepancy is considered most likely to be due to differences in the relaxation times in tension and shear.

INTRODUCTION

The design of bonded joints in composite materials requires a knowledge of the mechanical behaviour of the adhesive as well as that of adherends. Traditionally, data for adhesives has been obtained from tests on bonded joints. Most of these tests are simple and the test pieces are easy to make, but the stress state in the adhesive is usually complex and the data obtained is of limited value for use in design [1,2]. In addition, the results often show large scatter and also vary with joint geometry and properties of the adherends. Improved tests have been developed but these are more difficult to conduct and require purpose built instruments to measure the small displacements that occur in the adhesive.

An alternative way to obtain the mechanical properties for the adhesive is to test specimens of the bulk material. However, controversy exists as to whether the data obtained in this way is in fact representative of the adhesive in the thin film form which exists in a joint [2,3,4,5,6]. In part, the lack of confidence in bulk adhesive data has resulted because of the different levels of cure that can occur in bulk specimens compared with joints, and because of differences in the size and quantity of defects in each case. The situation has been compounded by the complex stress state which occurs even in simple joints and the varying rates at which the adhesive deforms in different

parts of the joint.

This work seeks to establish whether bulk adhesive testing can provide reliable tensile data to be used in composite joint design. In the initial phase of the work, which is described in this paper, data obtained from bulk adhesive testing was used to predict the behaviour of joints loaded in shear. The predictions were compared with the measured behaviour of the joints. The bulk adhesive data was obtained from uniaxial tensile specimens while the joints examined were standard thick adherend lap shear specimens. Ultra-microindentation testing [7] was also used to compare the properties of the adhesive in bulk samples with the 'in situ' properties of the adhesive in a joint.

Adhesives, being polymeric materials, are viscoelastic in nature and their mechanical properties vary with time. Under such circumstances, in order to determine shear behaviour from tensile data, it is necessary to use the concept of effective stress and effective strain. This was done using Tobolsky's assumption of equivalent relaxation times in shear and tension [8]. The equivalent strain rate is dependent on the yield criterion used and both the von Mises and Drucker's yield criteria were examined.

According to the von Mises yield criterion, the effective stress and effective strain are given by:

$$\sigma_{eff} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2(1+\nu)}} \sqrt{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)^2 + (\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_3)^2 + (\epsilon_3 - \epsilon_1)^2} \quad (2)$$

The effective stress and effective strain have been derived by Gali, for Drucker's yield criterion, as follows [9]:

$$\sigma_{eff} = \frac{\sigma_{by} + \sigma_{cy}}{2\sqrt{2}\sigma_{cy}} \sqrt{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2} + \frac{\sigma_{cy} - \sigma_{by}}{2\sigma_{cy}} (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3) \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{1}{(1+\nu)} \frac{(\sigma_{cy} + \sigma_{by})}{2\sqrt{2}\sigma_{cy}} \sqrt{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)^2 + (\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_3)^2 + (\epsilon_3 - \epsilon_1)^2} + \frac{1}{(1-2\nu)} \frac{(\sigma_{cy} - \sigma_{by})}{2\sigma_{cy}} (\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2 + \epsilon_3) \quad (4)$$

Table 1 lists the effective stress and effective strain for the von Mises and Drucker's yield criteria for uniaxial tension and pure shear.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

MATERIAL

The adhesive used in this work was a 177°C cure unsupported film adhesive, FM300U, supplied by Cytec. It is an epoxy-based adhesive, toughened with an elastomer, and can be used for both secondary bonding and co-curing.

Table 1. Effective Stress and Effective Strain for Von Mises Yield Criterion and Drucker's Yield Criterion for Uniaxial Tension and Pure Shear

Yield Criterion	Von Mises Yield Criterion	Drucker's Yield Criterion
Uniaxial Tension	$\sigma_{eff} = \sigma_t$	$\sigma_{eff} = \sigma_t$
	$\epsilon_{eff} = \epsilon_t$	$\epsilon_{eff} = \epsilon_t$
Pure Shear	$\sigma_{eff} = \sqrt{3} \tau_{xy}$	$\sigma_{eff} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \frac{(\sigma_{by} + \sigma_{cy})}{\sigma_{cy}} \tau_{xy}$
	$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \frac{\gamma_{xy}}{(1+\nu)}$	$\epsilon_{eff} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{(\sigma_{cy} + \sigma_{by})}{(1+\nu)\sigma_{cy}} \gamma_{xy}$
Equivalent Strain Rate	$\frac{d\epsilon_t}{dt} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2(1+\nu)} \frac{d\gamma_{xy}}{dt}$	$\frac{d\epsilon_t}{dt} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{(\sigma_{cy} + \sigma_{by})}{(1+\nu)\sigma_{cy}} \frac{d\gamma_{xy}}{dt}$

BULK ADHESIVE TENSILE TESTS

Bulk adhesive specimens were prepared from 16 layers of FM300U stacked in a mould and cured in a hydrostatic press at 177°C for 1 hour. Dog-bone tensile specimens were machined from the cured panels and tested at three constant strain rates at room temperature. The specimens were of the same dimensions as those used by Jeandrau [2] except for the thickness which was 1.5mm. Six samples were tested at each strain rate and full tensile stress-strain curves were obtained.

Poisson's ratio was measured using a 2-element 90° 'tee' rosette strain gauge. The strain gauge was glued onto the gauge section of the bulk adhesive dog-bone sample. Strain signals from the two elements were measured and digitised using a HBM40 strain amplifier. Poisson's ratio was determined by dividing the longitudinal strain by the transverse strain.

THICK ADHEREND LAP SHEAR TESTS

Thick adherend lap shear tests were conducted using symmetric thick adherend lap joint specimens made from hardened tool steel. The specimens were the same as those used by Chalkley and Chiu [10]. Two layers of FM300U were laid onto the bond area of the dried specimen. The assembled specimens were then vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave at 177°C for 1 hour. After curing, the spew fillet was removed using a scraper and a knife.

The thick adherend lap shear joints were tested at three different constant strain rates, 0.1734/min, 0.01734/min, and 0.001734/min. A minimum of two specimens were tested at each rate. A KGR-1 extensometer was mounted onto the thick adherend specimens to measure the shear strain.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

To predict the behaviour of the lap joint, a three-dimensional finite element (FE) model was created using Strand 6.1. Tensile stress-strain curves from the uniaxial tensile tests were used as the adhesive properties. Nonlinear elastic analyses were conducted using both the von Mises and Drucker's yield criteria. In the analysis using Drucker's yield criterion, it was necessary to obtain the coefficient of the octahedral shear stress component and that of the hydrostatic stress component, and these were determined experimentally using the method described in Reference 9, which utilises the combined results from tension and shear tests. In the model, shear stresses were determined by dividing the applied load by the bond area. Shear strains were calculated for the positions where the KGR-1 extensometer was attached.

ULTRA-MICROINDENTATION TESTS

As an independent method of comparing the behaviour of adhesive in the bulk with the in situ behaviour of adhesive in a joint, ultra-microindentation tests were carried out both on bulk samples and on adhesive in bonded joints, using a UMIS 2000 ultra-microindentation system. Details of the system are given elsewhere [7]. A spherically-tipped diamond indenter of 20 micrometer nominal spherical radius was used for all tests. A loading partial-unloading cycle was used. The joint samples were standard single lap shear specimens made with aluminium adherends and cured under similar conditions to the bulk adhesive specimens. Samples from the bonded joints were indented with arrays of indentations in the adhesive. The distance between indentations ranged from 40 μm to 50 μm . Six indentations were made in a line at 40 μm spacing across the bulk adhesive samples.

The resulting force versus depth of penetration curves were analysed to determine an effective modulus E^* for each indentation. Assuming the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the diamond indenter to be 1000 GPa and 0 respectively, and using the experimentally determined value of Poisson's ratio of the adhesive, the elastic modulus of FM300U was calculated using the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{E^*} = \frac{1 - \nu_D^2}{E_D} + \frac{1 - \nu_F^2}{E_F} \quad (5)$$

where E_D , ν_D are the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the diamond indenter and E_F , ν_F are the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of the adhesive FM300U.

RESULTS

TENSILE STRESS-STRAIN CURVES OF FM300U

Fig.1 shows the true tensile stress-strain curves of FM300U at three different strain rates. The Young's modulus and yield strength varied significantly with strain rate, the higher the strain rate the higher the Young's modulus and tensile yield stress. Table 2 lists the mean and standard deviation of the Young's modulus and tensile yield stress.

Figure 1. True Tensile Stress-Strain Curves of FM300U at Three Different Strain Rates

Table 2. Tensile Properties of FM300U at Three Different Strain Rates

Tensile Strain Rate (/min)	Young's Modulus (MPa)		Tensile Yield Stress (MPa)	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
0.001	2670	8	65.94	0.18
0.01	2703	35	70.17	0.18
0.1	2966	36	74.41	0.35

The tensile yield stress was found to vary linearly with the log of strain rate as given below:

$$\sigma_{ty} = 78.639 + 1.839 \ln\left(\frac{de_t}{dt}\right) \quad (6)$$

where σ_{ty} is the tensile yield stress, and $\frac{de_t}{dt}$ is the tensile strain rate. Poisson's ratio was found

to be 0.3634 and was independent of the strain rate.

SHEAR STRESS-STRAIN CURVES FOR FM300U

The measured shear stress-strain curves of FM300U at three different strain rates are shown in Fig.2. The shear modulus and shear yield stress were found to increase significantly with increased strain rate. Table 3 lists the mean and standard deviation of the shear modulus and the shear yield stress.

Table 3. Shear Properties of FM300U at Three Different Strain Rate

Shear Strain Rate (/min)	Shear Modulus (MPa)		Shear Yield Stress (MPa)	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
0.001734	1034	11	38.72	0.16
0.01734	1165	14	41.55	0.07
0.1734	1290	32	44.06	0.56

Figure 2. Shear Stress-Strain Curves of FM300U at Three Different Strain Rates

An empirical equation was derived for the shear yield stress as a function of the log of strain rate, giving:

$$\tau_{ty} = 46.530 + 1.233 \ln\left(\frac{d\gamma_t}{dt}\right) \tag{7}$$

where τ_{ty} is the tensile yield stress, and $\frac{d\gamma_t}{dt}$ is the shear strain rate.

FINITE ELEMENT PREDICTIONS

Figure 3. Finite Element Predictions of Thick Adherend Lap Shear Joint Tests Using Von Mises Yield Criterion and Drucker's Yield Criterion

The finite element predictions for the thick adherend lap shear joint using both the von Mises and Drucker's yield criteria are shown in Fig.3. Both yield criteria give good predictions of the yield stress with less than 2% error. However, the shear modulus was underestimated by approximately 16%.

ULTRA-MICROINDENTATION RESULTS

The elastic moduli for the bulk adhesive and for a bonded joint, as determined from ultra-microindentation tests, are listed in Table 4. The elastic modulus of the bulk adhesive was 3% higher than that of the bonded joint. While this difference is small, the results indicate that it is significant.

Table 4. Mean and Standard Deviation (S.D.) of Elastic Modulus for Bulk Adhesive and that of Bonded Joint

Material	Elastic Modulus (MPa)	
	Mean	S.D.
Bulk Adhesive	2269	9
Bonded Joint	2204	5

DISCUSSION

The results indicate that bulk adhesive data can be used to accurately predict the yield strength of the adhesive in a joint at least for the stress state which exists in the thick adherend shear specimen. The predicted behaviour is insensitive to the yield criterion used because the hydrostatic component is minimal in this case. Further work is under way using butt joints in which the hydrostatic component is significant.

While the yield strength is accurately predicted, the modulus of the adhesive in the thick adherend specimen is substantially underestimated and this discrepancy is surprising in view of the only small difference between the values of the modulus for the bulk and in situ adhesive obtained using the ultra-microindentation test. The difference in level of agreement obtained from the two independent tests may be due to different levels of cure in the thick adherend specimen used to obtain the experimental joint data and the lap shear specimen from which the micro-indentation results were obtained. Indeed, the small difference between the results for the bulk and in situ adhesive detected in the micro-indentation test is considered most likely to arise in this way. However, the experimental joint results give a modulus substantially higher than the value predicted from the bulk adhesive tests while the microindentation results indicate that the modulus in the joint is lower than that of the bulk adhesive and it is difficult to see how deviations in both directions could be explained in a similar way. An alternative explanation may be that the assumption of equivalent relaxation times in tension and shear is not valid and that the usual relationship between the tensile and shear moduli,

$$E = 2G(1+\nu) \tag{8}$$

no longer applies.

CONCLUSIONS

- The mechanical properties of FM300U are strain rate dependent.

- Bulk adhesive tensile data provides a reliable estimate of the yield behaviour of the adhesive in the thick adherend shear test indicating its usefulness for joint analysis and design.
- The yield behaviour is reliably predicted using both the von Mises and Drucker's yield criteria.
- The bulk adhesive data substantially underpredicts the modulus of the adhesive in the thick adherend test. This may indicate that the assumption of equivalent relaxation times in tension and shear is not valid for the adhesive used and that the normal relationship between the tensile and shear moduli no longer applies.

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